

IMPACT OF COMPUTER ASSISTED AUDIT TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES (CAATT_s) ON FRAUD DETECTION: EVIDENCE FROM DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Businesses across the world have seen tremendous changes as a result of information technology and have drastically altered the way transactions are documented, tracked, and reported in the accounting profession. The study investigated the influence of Computer Assisted Audit Tools and Techniques (CAATTs) on fraud detection in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks. Survey research design was adopted and a structured questionnaire was used to gather data from respondents through a conveniently sampling technique. 198 auditors and managers in the big-four audit firms and the twenty listed deposit money banks, were sampled. The data gathered was presented using descriptive statistical tools (frequency and percentages) and analyzed using the Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), with the aid of the SmartPLS-3 software. The result of the analysis revealed a significant and positive effect of CAATTs components on fraud detection ($\beta=0.458$, $t = 6.172$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that CAATTs significantly influence the detection of fraud, among Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. Therefore, it was recommended that stakeholders should implement policies that will drive the use of CAATTs for forensic auditing activities in the Nigerian banking sector. Furthermore, the government should support the efforts of the banks in fighting fraud by facilitating whistle-blowing policies and encouraging the creation of fraud-hotlines in the banks.

Keywords: CAATTs; Audit Software; Embedded Audit Software; Audit Command Language; Interactive data extraction and analysis; Bank Fraud.

INTRODUCTION

In the last few decades, the use of Information Technology (IT) in auditing has increased dramatically, transforming the audit process landscape and presenting both prospects and challenges for auditors (Raed & Wadi, 2018; Mahzan & Veerankutty, 2011), to the point where auditors have no choice but to use IT tools. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has played an increasingly crucial role in designing modern business organizations in order to achieve short and long-term goals. In practically all human pursuits, technology has played a crucial role (Ofurun & Ogbonna, 2008; Appah & Emeh, 2011; Agbatogun, Ajelabi, Oyewusi & Inegbedion, 2011). Computer Assisted Audit Tools and Techniques (CAATTs) are a type of IT capability that is supported by professional auditors and suggested by Auditing Standards to make their jobs easier (Ebimobowei, Ogbonna & Enebraye, 2013; Janvrin, Lowe & Bierstaker, 2014a, b).

CAATTs and audit automation are computerized technologies or approaches that improve the efficiency and effectiveness of audit functions (Cigna, Djuric, & Sigheartau, 2016; Gantz,

2014; Okunbor & Obaretin, 2010; Coderre, 2009). In order to conduct comprehensive or operational audits, auditors are frequently required to access and use data directly from client systems. Using computer-assisted approaches, auditors are able to increase their capacity to critically examine data and information and execute their own tasks more rationally (Mahzan & Veerankutty, 2011). CAATs have been tried and failed by several organizations (Dias & Marques, 2018). Improved awareness on CAATs, including their origins, uses, limitations, hazards, and so on, is the first step toward a continual comprehension of their ever-changing capabilities (Dias & Marques, 2018; KPMG, 2015; Li, Dai, Gershberg & Vasarhelyi, 2018). Auditing procedures usually involve forensic examinations of financial transaction, which can enhance fraud detection, hence the use of CAATs. Fraud is one of the most severe issues that any business encounters, as it not only causes financial loss but also damages the company's reputation (Popoola, Fakunle, Omole & Oyedeji, 2018). A survey by the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners' (ACFE, 2016) revealed that an organization has the ability to lose 5 percent of its earnings to fraud, each year. Scholars have posited fraud as the number one enemy of business and no company is immune, as it can be found in every facet of life (Inaya & Isito, 2016; Udeh & Ugwu, 2018). Moreover, numerous writers, including Owojori and Asaolu (2009), Kasum (2009), Okoye and Akamobi (2009), Owolabi (2010), Izedomin and Mgbame (2011), and Gbegi and Adebisi (2014), have demonstrated in their own investigations that the incidences of fraud and fraudulent activities in Nigeria are on the rise.

The banking sector, in particular, appears to be one of the world's havens for fraud and criminal activities, owing to the high volume of transactions and big amount of currency handled, which makes it especially enticing to fraudsters (Olukotun, Ademola, Olusegun & Olorunfemi, 2013). The roles of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in the economy, such as credit provision, savings mobilization, capital provision for development, encouragement of trading activities through the use of various payment instruments, managerial advice to industrialists and financial advice cannot be over-emphasized (Etuk, 2011). Deposit money banks are also responsible for providing credit to SMEs and other areas of the economy. As a result, the prevalence of fraud may jeopardize the sector's integrity and long-term viability, as well as its ability to perform these functions effectively and sustainably. Therefore, more complex forensic auditing techniques, such as CAATs, are required to detect frauds and forgeries (Okoye & Abegi, 2013; Apostolou Alfred & Francis, 2017; Towler, White, Ballantyne, Searston, Martire & Kemp, 2018). The objective of this study is to examine the impact of CAATs in the fraud detection among DMBs in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Computer Assisted Audit Tools and Techniques (CAATs)

CAATs are technologies used to filter transactions with certain characteristics, provide confirmation of control efficacy, and examine inventory existence and completeness in every company environment and industry sector (Curtis & Payne, 2008; Janvrin et al, 2009; AICPA, 2011). They allow the company's auditor to work more efficiently and effectively, while the extracted and summarized data provided by the tool aids management in making choices and

keeping business secrets hidden (Zhao, Yen & Chang, 2004; Debreceeny, Lee, Neo & Shuling, 2004; Wadesango & Nyakurera, 2020). In auditing process, CAATs have become identical with data analytics (Ahmad, Markkula & Oivo, 2013; Ahmi & Kent, 2012; Ahmi, Saidin & Abdullah, 2014). They are used to directly examine an application's internal logic and analytical data, as well as deduce application logic indirectly (Cao, Chychyla & Stewart, 2015; Chan, Chiu & Vasarhelyi, 2018; Moffitt, Rozario & Vasarhelyi, 2018; Kokina & Davenport, 2017; Alles & Gray, 2016). As a result, any firm's accounting department will be capable of producing more analytical results and forensic accounting with more and larger analyses, increasing the efficiency, effectiveness, and productivity of the auditors' work (Akabom-Ita, 2012). Scholars have identified four major CAATs components, namely; Audit Software, Embedded audit software, Audit Command Language and Interactive data extraction and analysis (IDEA) (Senft, Gallegos & Davis, 2014; Coderre, 2015; 2009).

Audit Software (AudSoft) is pre-packaged, off-the-shelf or custom build software tailored to check a client's system. Embedded audit software (EAS) is software that requires the integration of a custom audit program into the client's accounting system (Debreceeny, Gray, Tham & Goh, 2005). Audit Command Language (ACL) provides data analytics, governance, risk management, and compliance (GRC) software, as well as risk and audit management consulting services (Baker, 2009; ACL Services Ltd, 2017). It is employed in the detection, prevention, and control of fraud. Interactive data extraction and analysis (IDEA) is one of a variety of powerful and easy-to-use technologies designed to help accounting and financial professionals improve their auditing capabilities, detect fraud, and follow documentation standards (Adeyemi, Mohammed, Ogundeyi & Tijani, 2014). The ease with which business fails has put a greater responsibility and duty on auditors, to equip themselves with the skills and tools to recognize and respond to signs of poor corporate governance, mismanagement, fraud, and other wrongdoings (Okunbor & Obaretin, 2010). As a result, more complex forensic auditing techniques, such as CAATs, are required to detect frauds and forgeries (Okoye & Abegi, 2013; Singleton, Singleton, Bologna & Lindquist, 2006).

Bank Fraud

Levi (2008) defined bank fraud as crimes involving deception or a conspiracy, as opposed to bank robbery or theft. Zgaris (2010) refers to it as a "white-collar crime," which implies a financially motivated, non-violent crime committed by workers of businesses and government agencies. In Nigeria, Owolabi (2010) submitted that large scale fraud among banks has resulted in the sector's insolvency. According to Akinyomi (2012), scammers in Nigeria (popularly known as Yahoo boys) frequently perpetrate bank frauds and work with corrupt bankers in the Western Union department/store to withdraw stolen money. Fraud is the number one enemy of business; no company is immune, and it can be found in every facet of life (Akinyomi, 2012; Owolabi, 2010). It is therefore a concern that traditional auditing and investigation had become ineffective and inefficient in detecting and preventing various types of fraudulent practices in recent years (Onuorah & Ebimobowei, 2012).

Empirical Review

Many scholars have investigated the role of CAATTs in fraud detection. Singleton, Todd, and Messina (2004) investigated utilization of CAATTs in uncovering fraud in the United States. The study identified Generalized Audit Software (GAS) as the most frequently used. In Malaysia, Moorthy, Seetharaman, Mohamed, Gopalan, and San (2011) conducted a study on the influence of Information Technology (IT) on Internal Audit and control processes. A survey on the auditors in selected companies revealed that IT has a significant impact on an organization's Internal Control mechanism. This result however precludes the effect of CAATTs on fraud detection. Pedrosa and Costa (2012) investigated the use and approaches of CAATTs in detecting fraud evidence gathered through interviews and document reviews in Portugal. The study revealed that CAATTs components are effective in detecting fraud. This further supported the findings of Popa, Moraru, Facane and Blidisel (2009), who opined that Interactive Data Extraction and Analysis (IDEA), Audit Command Language (ACL), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), and other CAATTs can detect fraud evidence. Similar results have also been established in other countries like United State (Sachin, Manish & Raj, 2014); Indian (Bhasin, 2016) and Jordan (Ahmad, Nidal, & Ezz, 2019). However, the work of Rindang and Synthia (2017) failed to support these results. The researchers investigated the use of Generalized Audit Software (GAS) in improving financial report lucidity and accountability by internal auditors of listed companies in Indonesia. Their findings revealed that the internal auditors are of the opinion that the auditing software does not significantly impact on their auditing activities.

In the Nigeria context only few studies have demonstrated the empirical relationship between CAATTs and fraud detection. Olanmi (2013) studied the influence of Computer Aided Audit Techniques on Fraud Detection among selected auditors in KPMG audit firm in Nigeria. The researcher observed that CAATTs has played a substantial role in fraud detection and may be utilized to improve auditor performance and financial report quality. The study is however limited to one large audit company (KPMG) making it difficult to generalize the finding. Amahalu, Abiahu, and Obi (2017) investigated the computerized and manual accounting processes of Nigeria's listed microfinance enterprises and opined that the computerized accounting system has positive impact on the profitability of the enterprises. Ogiriki and Appah (2018) studied the impact of forensic accounting and auditing techniques on public sector fraud detection in Nigeria. Using an ex-post facto research approach, the researcher observed a strong correlation between auditing techniques and fraud detection. The study concluded that accounting and auditing techniques significantly influence fraud detection in the Nigerian public sector. Such investigation is yet to be replicated in the banking sector of the country, hence the need for this research.

Theoretical Framework

The Diffusion of Innovation and the Fraud Diamond theories are the underpinnings of this study. The Diffusion of innovation, according to Rogers (2003), is a type of communication concerned with the spread of new ideas, objects, or practices, including computerized accounting system, among organizations. The Fraud Diamond theory, postulated by Cressey

(1971), stated that fraud thrives in any business, regardless of the amount of control mechanism in place. Various scholars have used these theories in studies which cut across individuals and institutional activities (Dearing & Cox, 2018; Zhang, Yu, Yan & Spil, 2015; Dearing, 2009; Kaminski, 2011). Both theories are therefore relevant to studies in the banking industry and hence adopted for this study. The hypothesis for the relationship between the study variables is thus stated in null form as;

H₀: CAATTs does not significantly influence fraud detection among DMBs in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional research survey was adopted in this study, in order to explore the relationship between the exploratory and predictive variables. The investigation was carried out in Lagos state, Nigeria, where the 20-listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) and the big-four audit firms have their headquarters (CBN, 2022). Therefore, population of the study includes auditors in the DMBs and the big four audit firms. Two hundred auditors were purposively selected for this study and primary data on the study variables were harvested through a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered through a convenience sampling technique to 160 auditors in the banks (8 auditors per bank) and 40 auditors in the audit firms (10 per firm). The questionnaire consists of two parts (A & B). Part A includes items on the social-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Part B includes items on the dimensions of the fraud constructs and the CAATTs components (Audit Software-Audsoft; Audit Command Language-ACL; Embedded Audit Software-EAS; and Interactive Data Extraction & Analysis-IDEA). Responses to the question items were captured on the 5-point Likert scale, ranging from Strongly Agree (SA=5) to Strongly Disagree (SD=1).

The PLS-SEM was used to specify the theoretical model and analysis was carried out using the SmartPLS-3 software. The Standardized Factor Loadings (SFLs), Cronbach Alpha statistics, Composite Reliability (CR) and Rho_A ratios were all computed in order to test the internal consistency of the measurement instrument. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values of the construct variables were used to test the convergent validity of their items. Chin (1988) recommends a minimum threshold of 0.5 for AVE. The Fornell-Larcker and Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) criteria were used to establish the discriminant validity of the constructs. The Fornell-Larcker criterion requires the square root of the AVEs to be greater than the inter-construct correlations (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Kline (2011) recommends HTMT value not more than 0.9. The bootstrapping process of 5000 in PLS-SEM was used to estimate the parameters of the structural model and test the hypothesis. The Standard Root Mean Residual (SRMR), R-squared value and Chi-square statistics were used to test the overall model fit. It is expected that CAATTs components will influence fraud detection.

RESULTS

The demographic analysis in Table 1 shows that 198 out of 200 copies of the questionnaire were properly filled and returned. This represents a response rate of 99%. The results show that more than half of the respondents are male (64%). The average age group of the respondents

is 35-45years (35.8%), while the number of years of experience as auditors varies with 55 (27.7%) below 5years, 48 (24.2%) between 6 to 10years, 41 (20.7%) between 11 to 15years and 54 (27.2%) above 15years. The result on professional qualification show that more than half of the respondents (59.6%) are professional accountants with ICAN/ACCA/ANAN qualification.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	127	64
Female	71	36
Age		
Below 35 years	65	33
35-45 years	71	35.8
45-55 years	51	25.7
Above 55 years	11	5.5
Experience		
Below 5 years	55	27.7
6 - 10 years	48	24.2
11 - 15 years	41	20.7
Above 15 years	54	27.2
Professional Qualifications		
ICAN/ACCA/ANAN	118	59.6
CIBN Only	23	11.6
ICT Certifications Only	18	9.1
Others	11	5.6
None	28	14.1

Assessment of the Measurement Model

Table 2 showed the items that were retained for each construct variable following the assessment of the measuring instruments.

Table 2: Constructs, items code and details of final measurement Items

Constructs	Items Code	Measurement items
FraudD	FD6	Reported cases of fraud is still high in banks despite adoption of CAATTs
	FD7	The security system (and poor internal control) in Nigerian banks, rather than usage of CAATTs is mostly responsible for fraud cases.
	FD8	The large volume of transactions in Banks despite the use of CAATTs makes fraud prevention stressful and difficult
	FD9	Most of the fraud cases in banks are perpetrated through the computer which CAATTs can detect easily.
AUD	AUD3	AuSoftware is easily accessible as off the shelf, packages or self-developed compared to other CAATTs types

	AUD4	Usage of AuSoftware enables scrutinization of large volume of data.
	AUD5	AuSoftware can detect fraud by making the auditor's job easier by picking test samples, detecting risk areas, and carrying out specific substantive procedures
	AUD7	AuSoftware can extract samples at random, based on pre-defined criteria; a given amount (below or over); dates; "calculating ratios and selecting indicators that fail to fulfill certain pre-defined criteria"; stratification of data (such as invoices by customer or age)
	AUD8	AuSoftware creates letters for customers and suppliers, as well as tracking transactions via a computerized system
	AUD10	AuSoftware is simple and easy to use
ACL	ACL2	ACL includes general modules for reading existing computer files and performing advanced data changes to complete audit requirements.
	ACL3	ACL enables auditors to perform operations such as data extraction, querying, manipulation, summarizing, and analysis all at the same time
	ACL4	Usage of ACL in my organization is fully supported by Management.
	ACL5	Management provides all necessary facilities and resources to support the use of ACL
	ACL6	The adoption of ACL in my organization and by most DMBs and Audit firms has helped them to perform efficiently and profitably.
	ACL7	ACL is meant to provide data analytics, governance, risk management, and compliance, as well as risk and audit management consulting services, in order to detect fraud in the bank's everyday financial operations as quickly as possible.
	ACL8	Judicious use of ACL is seen as a pre-requisite to fraud detection and prevention in my bank
	ACL9	ACL assists auditors in detecting financial statement "misstatements and achieving the goals of validity, completeness, ownership, valuation, correctness, classification, and disclosure of accounting software data".
	ACL11	The need for frequent update of the ACL may make its adoption inefficient.
	ACL12	ACL is seen as an alternative to internal control system and management oversight in banks.
EAS	EAS1	EAS is a fraud-detection audit program that is embedded in the client's accounting system
	EAS2	Most Nigerian Banks/Audit firm's management find auditing and operations to be very easy because of the use of EAS
	EAS4	EAS is designed to execute specific audit duties and has the benefit of being able to be turned on and off by the auditor at any time during the accounting year
	EAS5	EAS enables the auditor to acquire relevant data on specific transactions for testing and to discover anomalies that need to be addressed during the final audit
	EAS6	Management is disposed to training relevant employees in my organization on EAS usage
	EAS7	The use of EAS has implications on level of clients' patronage and profitability

	EAS8	The use of EAS has implications on level of clients' patronage and profitability
	EAS10	EAS is used widely in Nigerian Deposit money banks and audit firms
	EAS11	The implementation of EAS in banks will improve audit efficiency and effectiveness
IDEA	IDEA1	IDEA is a "sophisticated and user-friendly application for accounting and financial professionals who want to improve their auditing capabilities, detect fraud, and meet documentation requirements".
	IDEA2	IDEA is an easy-to-use program
	IDEA3	IDEA effortlessly imports data from practically any source to analyze big data sets, visualize insights, and automate repeated processes without the need for programming
	IDEA4	IDEA allows users to quickly and easily import nearly unlimited data from a variety of sources (ERP systems, spreadsheets, old mainframes, T&E applications, flat and printed files, and more).
	IDEA5	IDEA helps to ensure the correctness of audit assessments and disclosures in published financial statements by providing read-only access
	IDEA6	IDEA may export data to Microsoft Access, XML, Text, Microsoft Word, PDF, Microsoft Excel, and pre-defined reports, among other formats.
	IDEA8	IDEA is adaptable to any environment, especially in the banking system
	IDEA9	The rampant incidences of cybercrime in Nigeria can be arrested using IDEA.

The standardized factor loadings (SFLs) for each item in the research questionnaire were computed the results presented in Table 3 showed that all the retained items have loadings higher than the 0.70 threshold. In addition, the Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability (CR) and Rho_A were computed in order to assess the internal consistency of the measuring instrument. Results in Table 3 revealed that both the Cronbach Alphas and the CR values of all the items are above the minimum acceptable value of 0.7, which establishes the reliability of the instrument. Similarly, all the Rho_A values are within the acceptable threshold of 0.70 to 0.99, which further confirms that the items in the instrument have no reliability problem.

Furthermore, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) results explain the convergent validity of the question items in relation to their construct. The AVEs of the construct variables in Table 3 are all above the minimum threshold of 0.50, which establishes their validity.

Table 3: Construct validity, Convergent validity, and reliability

Constructs	Items Code	SFLs	Cronbach's Alpha	Rho_A	CR	AVE					
FraudD	FD6	0.750	0.725	0.726	0.829	0.548					
	FD7	0.710									
	FD8	0.770									
	FD9	0.731									
ACL	ACL2	0.797	0.941	0.946	0.95	0.655					
	ACL3	0.847									
	ACL4	0.823									
	ACL5	0.794									
	ACL6	0.859									
	ACL7	0.807									
	ACL8	0.846									
	ACL9	0.842									
	ACL11	0.747									
	ACL12	0.722									
	AUD	AUD3					0.776	0.886	0.895	0.912	0.635
		AUD4					0.780				
AUD5		0.806									
AUD7		0.826									
AUD8		0.826									
AUD10		0.764									
EAS1		0.817									
EAS	EAS2	0.857	0.949	0.951	0.957	0.711					
	EAS4	0.857									
	EAS5	0.813									
	EAS6	0.884									
	EAS7	0.846									
	EAS8	0.847									
	EAS10	0.820									
	EAS11	0.846									
IDEA	IDEA1	0.895	0.961	0.963	0.967	0.786					
	IDEA2	0.886									
	IDEA3	0.910									
	IDEA4	0.926									
	IDEA5	0.856									
	IDEA6	0.888									
	IDEA8	0.875									
	IDEA9	0.853									

The result of the Fornell-Larcker criterion in Table 4 shows that the square roots of the AVEs (bolded) are greater than the inter-construct correlations, indicating that the constructs do not have discriminant validity problem. Similarly, Table 5 reveals that Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratios are all below the maximum threshold of 0.9. This further establishes the discriminant validity condition of the constructs.

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	ACL	AUD	EAS	FraudD	IDEA
ACL	0.809				
AUD	0.585	0.797			
EAS	0.655	0.63	0.843		
FraudD	0.349	0.417	0.392	0.74	
IDEA	0.498	0.622	0.681	0.424	0.887

Values on the diagonal (bolded) are square root of the AVE while the off-diagonal are correlations.

Table 5: Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) criterion

	ACL	AUD	EAS	FraudD	IDEA
ACL					
AUD	0.639				
EAS	0.689	0.688			
FraudD	0.408	0.508	0.469		
IDEA	0.521	0.674	0.716	0.503	

Structural Equation Model

Figure 1: PLS Algorithms

Table 6: Model fit/predictive relevance

Model fit	Value	Benchmark	Source
SRMR	0.058	<0.08	Garson (2016)
R ²	0.21	>0.26	Cohen (1988)
Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)	0.109	>0	Hair et al (2019)
Chi-Square	1504.987		
		HI ₉₅	
d _{ULS} (d _{ULS} <HI ₉₅)	1.336	<1.744	Benitez et al., 2020
d _G (d _G <HI ₉₅)	0.999	<1.269	Benitez et al., 2020

The Standard Root Mean Residual (SRMR) value of the model is 0.058 which is less than the 0.08 benchmark, thus indicating a good model fit. The model also satisfy the $dULS < HI95$ and $dG < HI95$ overall model fit conditions. The R-squared value of 0.21 implies that the latent variables (AUD, ACL, EAS, and IDEA) explain 21.0% of the variance in the exploratory variable (fraud detection). Although, Cohen (1988) recommends a minimum acceptable threshold of 0.26, Ali et al. (2016) argues that R-squared value is contextual and relative to the field of study. To further establish the predictive importance of the factors, the Q^2 score was computed and the result (0.109) suggests that the model has predictive relevance.

Table 7: Weights of first order constructs on the second-order construct

Second-order construct	First order constructs	Weight	t-value
CAATTs Components	ACL	0.830	26.722*
	AUD	0.788	19.711*
	EAS	0.897	59.183*
	IDEA	0.837	29.190*

Notes: Critical t-values. *2.58 (P < 0.01)

The result from Table 7 reveals that the weights of the first order constructs are all significant. In addition, EAS has the highest outer weight of 0.897 on the second order construct, while the effect of AUD appears to be the smallest (0.788).

Table 8: Hypothesis Testing

Structural estimates				f ²	Confidence intervals		Decision
Path	β	t-value	p-value		2.50%	97.50%	
H2: CAATTs → Fraud D	0.458	6.172*	0.000	0.267	0.296	0.586	Supported

*p < 0.01, Significance (2-tailed)

The result of the structural estimates reveals a positive regression coefficient ($\beta = 0.458$) and the t-value ($t = 6.172$) is statistically significant at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$). This implies that CAATTs components (ACL, EAS, AudSoft, and IDEA) have a direct and significant effect on fraud detection. The confidence interval further support this significant relationship with an acceptable range of values (lower bound = 0.296 and upper bound = 0.586).

The summary of the result shows that the components of CAATTs significantly influence the detection of fraud amongst Deposit Money Bank in Nigeria. This finding agrees with those of Pedrosa and Costa (2012); Popa, Moraru, Facane and Blidisel (2009); Sachin, Manish and Raj, (2014) and Bhasin (2016). However, the finding disagrees with Rindang and Synthia (2017).

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The study investigated the influence Computer Assisted Audit Tools and Techniques (CAATTs) on fraud detection among Nigerian Deposit Money Banks. The four components (ACL, EAS, AudSoft, and IDEA) were used as dimensions of CAATTs. Question items were

developed for the construct variables (CAATTs components & fraud). The result of the analysis revealed that CAATTs component significantly influence fraud detection. Therefore, the study concludes that CAATTs is effective in the detection of fraud amongst Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The study recommends effective implementation of policies on the use of CAATTs for forensic auditing activities in the Nigerian banking sector. Banks and auditing firms should invest more in the acquisition of CAATTs components in order to aid fraud detections. Furthermore, the government can support the efforts of the banks in fighting fraud by facilitating whistle-blowing policies and encouraging the creation of fraud-hotlines in the banks.

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